

CHALLENGES IN BINAURAL CONVERSION OF MULTICHANNEL ELECTROACOUSTIC COMPOSITIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides a practical investigation and critical reflection on the challenges that arise when implementing a binaural conversion workflow for multichannel electroacoustic compositions. Using the specific example of the 3D AudioSpace on soundingfuture.com, the various technical and artistic considerations that arise will be discussed when adapting spatial audio works for listening through headphones.

While it does not present new research, it documents the decision-making process and practical solutions as a technical report. Particular attention is given to the artistic implications of these technical decisions, especially in terms of preserving compositional intent when introducing room virtualization and spatial processing. The results and recommendations presented here are intended to serve as a practical guide for similar implementation projects, while contributing to a broader discussion on standards and practices for binaural conversion of electroacoustic music.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context: The Sounding Future Platform

Sounding Future¹ is a bilingual online platform (EN/DE) created by Fränk Zimmer that presents technical and artistic innovations in music and audio technology. The 3D AudioSpace², a new audio streaming platform for on-demand playback provides artists from all over the world a stage on which they can showcase their works in high-quality binaural 3D audio for headphones. This makes immersive sound accessible to a global audience - without the need for special hardware or applications³. Related streaming platforms include HOAST⁴, as described in [1] and the Cat3DA player [2], implemented on the website of the Verband Deutscher Tonmeister⁵ that allows for

¹ www.soundingfuture.com

² <https://audiospace.soundingfuture.com/>

³ This realization was conceived by Malham back in 1995: "It will also be necessary to get concertgoers to wear headphones. However, such an approach may be more acceptable in the context of concerts broadcast over the World-Wide Web" (Malham and Myatt, 1995, p. 61)

⁴ <https://hoast.iem.at/>

⁵ <https://tonmeister.org>

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camera-based tracking with activatable room acoustic rendering of different rooms.

In order to present the works in the 3D AudioSpace, the multichannel compositions are first converted into a binaural format through a manual process, which is described in detail later.

1.2 Common Issues in Binaural Reproduction

With the increasing importance of binaural audio due to the demand for VR and AR applications, but also as an extremely practical and cost-effective solution compared to multichannel speaker configurations, the inherent problems of playback via headphones resurface. Although these issues are well documented, there are not yet satisfactory solutions to all of them.

In-Head Localization (IHL) describes the sensation that sounds are perceived inside the head instead of being externalized (i.e., from outside the head); this perceived localization is not strictly binary but rather exists on a continuum. [3, 4]. There are several explanations for this phenomenon, one of which is the Room Divergence Effect (RDE). It describes a perceptual conflict that occurs when binaural acoustic spatial information indicates one environment while visual and proprioceptive inputs indicate another [5, 6]. To limit this discrepancy, it can be a good idea to adapt the room size to the personal living space, e.g., in binaural virtualization.

Front-Back Confusion is the inability of the listener to distinguish between sounds coming from the front and from the back. This is usually remedied by subtle head movements that eliminate ambiguities in the time differences between front and back [7–9].

These issues result in an excessively wide sound stage, where sound sources are predominantly perceived from the sides. Frontal sounds, in contrast, are not perceived as originating from a distance but rather as localized within the listener's head. This is confirmed by [10], which showed that binaural cues from reflections (which are usually absent in binaural playback) are more important for the externalization of frontal sources than for lateral ones.

Given these challenges, which are unrelated to the perception of sounds in nature or music performances, it is remarkable that listeners have become so accustomed to the distinctive sound of headphones. This issue is rarely discussed outside of active research in this field. Never-

theless, the possibility of achieving a comparable listening experience to that of a high-quality multichannel system using headphones should encourage closer investigation of this issue and the development of pragmatic solutions.

1.3 Available Technical Solutions

Most of the above problems can be addressed with a combination of techniques, but not all of them are practical. One of them are personalized Head-Related Transfer Functions (HRTFs), which accurately model the individual reflections of the ears, head, and torso, and thus the coloration of the incoming sound, but the extensive measurement procedure remains time-consuming and complex [11]. Various methods can streamline this process, including ideas for personalizing generic HRTF data, selecting from a database of non-individual HRTFs, or simply adapting to a generic HRTF dataset [11–13].

Head tracking can partially mitigate front-back confusion, as the sound sources remain stationary and do not move with the head, thereby reducing the problem of in-head localization. [7, 14]. This technology is already implemented in some headphones or earphones, but can also be purchased as a separate device. In [15] the idea of modulating directivity and in [16] the spatial position of the sound source to improve externalization was investigated with negative results, which was also demonstrated in [9], in which only a small improvement in perceived externalization was found for large source movements.

Another approach that has gained interest in recent years is binaural virtualization. In this method, loudspeakers are acoustically virtualized together with a room and the corresponding reflections from the walls, thus modelling the acoustic behaviour of real loudspeakers in listening rooms. A relevant approach was proposed in [17]. Adding reverberant acoustic information to otherwise dry sounds significantly improves localization, as it situates the sounds within an acoustic context and provides the human auditory system with additional spatial cues [14]. Best et al. conclude in [4] with reference to several sources that “reverberant sounds are more likely than anechoic sounds to be perceived as externalized.” Another option would be to record Binaural Impulse Responses (BRIRs) and use them as convolution sources [18], which is the same technique used in the Binaural Renderer of the Audio Definition Model (ADM) [19].

2. PRELIMINARY CONSIDERATIONS

Currently, Sounding Future’s AudioSpace does not offer the option to enable head tracking, e.g., via a webcam, nor the possibility to import personal HRTF files. To provide a binaural experience that mitigates some of the challenges mentioned above, but also offers listeners a variety of choices, three different formats are offered on the platform: *Stereo* for playback on speakers, *Binaural*, which contains the binaurally decoded compositions, and *Binaural+*, where the tracks are virtualized, a process that requires some prior consideration.

2.1 Virtualization

When converting multichannel compositions into binaural using virtualization (as described in Section 1.3), some interesting questions arise, especially regarding the extent to which this method should influence or change the sound of the original composition. One could argue that the ideal listening space is an anechoic chamber, which is designed to have no reflections above a certain limit frequency (even studio speakers are optimized by manufacturers in anechoic chambers), but it turns out that listening to music in such an unnatural environment poses several problems, especially in the context of Ambisonics (the format many composers choose when working with multiple speakers [20]). Ambisonics works best with a slight reverberation, as this compensates for the shortcomings of the format in the form of spatial aliasing due to the truncation of spherical harmonics (in a concert situation, typically up to 7th order is used) [21, 22]. Adding virtual reverberation to a composition that already contains very specific virtual spaces seems problematic. But that would also mean that any concert space alters the work in an undesirable way, an aspect that is not normally perceived as such. Choral music was and is written specifically for large spaces, and one can generally assume that the particularities of concert spaces are consciously or unconsciously taken into account during the composition process [23]. In addition, every composer of electroacoustic music must deal with the task and uncertainty of transferring a work from the studio to another listening or concert space. This is especially true for composers working with Ambisonics, where the order and weighting of the decoder must be adjusted for each new loudspeaker setting (as Barrett emphasizes, e.g., in [24]).

2.2 Other Enhancements

For the process of converting multichannel compositions into binaural formats for the AudioSpace, the author decided not to experiment further or explore alternative methods and enhancements, as they change the compositional work to a greater extent. However, to complete the topic, other possible methods that alter the sound of the composition are briefly discussed, as they may still be of interest to composers converting their pieces to binaural.

Directional bands were first described by Blauert in [25] and further discussed in e.g., [26]. These frequency bands, especially between 2–4 kHz and 7–9 kHz, have an increased directional sensitivity due to the acoustic properties of the pinna and other head-related transfer functions, which allows a more accurate determination of the sound source position in three-dimensional space. In [27] a simple high-shelf filter was discussed, which is helpful in solving the problem of front-back confusion. Additionally, there are spatial localization cues at around 7–8 kHz for sounds that appear above the listener. These cues are relatively stable for the average listener (which can be observed when averaging HRTF data) and can be exploited to enhance the perception of elevated sound sources.

When working with filters on a composition, the issue of changing the compositional intent arises again. It remains to be determined if front-back confusion poses a greater problem than the sound coloration that results from its mitigation. One can assume that most composers work with the entire sphere/hemisphere, so emphasizing certain directions seems counterintuitive. However, a closer look at binaural playback shows that correction in this area may be necessary. As mentioned earlier, playback through headphones tends to stretch the musical stage very wide, with sounds appearing mainly to the left and right and not being externalized to the same extent at the front or rear. This could be seen as a change in compositional intent caused by the format itself. Nevertheless, it seems that both listeners and composers are accustomed to the confusion between the front and back, as well as the unnatural widening of the sound stage. As such, they are more willing to accept these as additional filtering and, consequently, alterations to the timbre. It can also be argued that truly precise localization accuracy is required for scientific purposes, but not to this extent when listening to electroacoustic compositions. These questions are still open and will probably be considered more in the future when a standard for binaural conversion of multichannel compositions is conceivable.

2.3 Channel-Based Audio Formats and a Case for Ambisonics

A key challenge that emerged during the design and implementation of the conversion workflow is the complexity of working with channel-based formats. For quadraphonic and octophonic speaker configurations, there is no standardized channel numbering system (e.g., clockwise, counterclockwise or pairwise), which is further complicated by alignment issues. For example, a speaker positioned front-left can be labelled either -30° or 30° , so it must be explicitly clarified whether the orientation follows a clockwise or counterclockwise convention⁶.

One might assume that channel-based formats that adhere to the Dolby standard would simplify the process. But even in these cases, many variables remain undefined. For the 5.1 format, for instance, there are two different channel numbering conventions, "Film" and "SMPTE", where the angles between the speakers also vary. It is therefore often unclear whether a composer worked in a studio where the front speakers were positioned at an angle of 22.5° or 30° and the rear speakers at an angle of -110° or -120° ⁷. In contrast, the Ambisonics B-Format is strictly defined by the AmbiX standard (or the older FUMA format) in terms of channel numbering (ACN) and channel normalization (SN3D). The speaker angles depend on the listener's speaker configuration or, in this case, on the virtual speaker configuration used in the conversion.

Due to the previously mentioned problems, the author suggests encoding channel-based electroacoustic compositions in Ambisonics for several reasons. Firstly, this ap-

⁶ A problem that can be addressed with using the ADM (ITU-R BS.2076) metadata format

⁷ <https://www.dolby.com/about/support/guide/surround-sound-speaker-setup/>

proach enables playback not only in the channel configurations for which the piece was originally composed, but also in other loudspeaker arrays. Secondly, it allows for the integration of Ambisonics effects like reverberation so that the pieces can be played back in smaller loudspeaker configurations while providing a fully immersive experience in larger, hemispherical arrays. Working in higher order Ambisonics enables quite a larger sweet area, which, in 5th order, already encompasses a large audience [28]. As the source width is considerably larger at lower orders, it becomes very narrow at higher orders—eventually approaching the size of the loudspeaker itself, while still maintaining the advantage that the source appears perceptually detached from the speakers [29].

Dave Malham, a central figure in the development and dissemination of Ambisonics stated in [30]: "For the composer in the studio to have a reasonably good idea of how sound objects will behave in the performance space, a system that allows for essentially seamlessly scalable loudspeaker configurations is necessary. This removes the changes produced as a result of differing numbers and positions of loudspeakers in the studio and performance spaces, leaving only the difference in actual acoustics to disrupt the composer's intentions."

3. IMPLEMENTATION: TECHNICAL PROCESS

As already mentioned, the AudioSpace of the Sounding Future web platform offers three different audio formats to choose from: *Stereo*, *Binaural* and *Binaural+*. The conversion approach for these different formats was conceived together with Fränk Zimmer and is explained in detail below. The findings regarding the chosen software and plug-ins in the following section were not based on a formal listening test protocol or statistical analysis; the results reflect personal impressions rather than objective findings.

3.1 Stereo

Rendering multichannel works in stereo is challenging, as full-sphere formats like Ambisonics must be reduced to a frontal presentation; however, the Ambisonics UHJ format provides a method for achieving this by enabling stereo-compatible distribution while preserving some spatial information. This format is a hierarchical surround sound encoding system developed in the 1970s by Gerzon for compatibility with mono and stereo playback systems [31]. It encodes spatial audio information in up to four channels (L, R, T, Q), whereby the usual two-channel format offers an improved stereo representation while remaining mono compatible. For the AudioSpace, the channel-based compositions were first converted to Ambisonics and then decoded using Blue Ripple Sound's O7A Decoder - UHJ Stereo VST plug-in.

3.2 Binaural

A binaural decoder converts Ambisonics audio (encoded as spherical harmonics) into two-channel audio optimized for headphone playback by applying a frequency-dependent decoding matrix derived from HRTFs. The

matrix combines the spatial information contained in the Ambisonics channels with HRTF data that captures how sound is naturally modified by the head, torso and ears. This process restores the essential spatial auditory cues - interaural time differences (ITDs), interaural level differences (ILDs) and spectral changes.

When comparing different binaural decoders, it became apparent that it is quite difficult to find a clear favourite. Our recommendation would be to choose the best-sounding decoder on a composition-by-composition basis. The ones we tested were from the SPARTA VST plug-in suite [32] and the IEM VST plug-in suite⁸. In this context, upmixing to higher orders of first or even third order Ambisonics compositions can also be considered (e.g., with plug-ins from the SPARTA suite).

To convert compositions to binaural formats without virtualization, channel-based formats (Quad, Octo or 5.1) had to be converted into Ambisonics and then decoded by a binaural decoder. To transcode these formats to Ambisonics, we chose Blue Ripple Sound's O7A Upmixers VST plug-in suite and the SPARTA AmbiBin Binaural decoder. This decoder offers Magnitude Least Square (MagLS), the current standard method for binaural decoding, and a generic HRTF, which we found to be the most favourable-sounding one in our listening impressions. The MagLS solution is an advanced optimization technique that focuses specifically on minimising magnitude errors at higher frequencies rather than trying to match both magnitude and phase of the HRTFs [33].

3.3 Binaural+

Binaural+ was chosen as the name for the virtualized binaural versions of the compositions. The '+' signifies the addition of a virtual room to the conversion process. For this format, we needed a solution that could be easily implemented in the conversion process and would give listeners a good impression of a virtual room. After reviewing several providers and their software, we opted for the Virtuoso VST plug-in from Applied Psychoacoustic Lab (APL) due to its flexibility and comprehensive functions. Other solutions include Nx from Waves Audio, Dear VR Monitor from Dear Reality and Immerse Virtual Studio from Embody.

When working with virtualization in practice, there are a few things to consider that can lead to interesting discussions. Firstly, there is the choice of a specific room geometry and characteristics in terms of absorption and other acoustic parameters. In the context of virtualization, it might be beneficial to use rooms that are closer to the standard sizes of living rooms in order to reduce the room divergence effect mentioned earlier. However, virtual rooms of this size proved too reverberant, so Virtuoso's default preset of the APL Listening Room was chosen, which models the actual APL's critical listening room that complies with the ITU-R BS.1116-3 recommendations. This is

⁸ <https://plugins.iem.at/>

a fairly large room, but with highly absorbent walls, resulting in a good spatial impression without too many acoustic reflections interfering with the direct sound.

The next question was which virtual speaker configuration to use. The Virtuoso VST plug-in offers a number of regular layouts, including T-designs with different channel counts. To decode compositions written in Ambisonics, we opted for the '26-point Lebedev design' because it has a higher density of virtual speakers than the other arrays and a more standard distribution of speakers than is usually found in real-world configurations. This means that the speakers are positioned closer to a production studio speaker array, such as a ring of speakers on the horizon and others at the top and bottom of the setup.

3.4 Binaural Decoding of Ambisonics Compositions

The Virtuoso VST plug-in expects standard speaker configurations such as 5.1 or quadraphonic as input format. To process Ambisonics compositions that are normally encoded in B-format, one must first decode them into one of the above configurations. Since we chose the 26-point Lebedev configuration as our default format, we had to find a way to decode the Ambisonics compositions into this configuration. The SPARTA ambiDEC Ambisonics decoder was chosen for this task as it offers several different decoding methods. After many listening sessions and some discussions with APL, we decided on Sampling Ambisonics Decoding (SAD) for both offered frequency bands, with the option AP (Amplitude Preserving) activated for the lower band and EP (Energy Preserving) for the upper band.

3.5 Transcoding of Channel-Based Formats

The Virtuoso VST plug-in has a number of input configurations for fixed channel formats (e.g., stereo, quad, 5.1) as well, so they could be converted directly into the *Binaural+* format. However, for *Stereo* and *Binaural* the formats had to be transcoded firstly to Ambisonics, which was done using the aforementioned O7A Upmixers VST plug-in suite from Blue Ripple Sound. These plug-ins have an option called *Inferred*, which sounded favourable in our listening sessions compared to the standard Ambisonics encoding methods. Normally, an Ambisonics encoder would encode sources as points in the soundfield (whose size depends on the Ambisonics order). However, the *Inferred* method also interpolates the space between the encoded sources, resulting in a more coherent representation of the virtual speaker array.⁹ For decoding to *Stereo*, the use of virtual microphone patterns as described in [34] can also be considered.¹⁰

The conversion of stereo compositions through Ambisonics to the output format *Binaural* was achieved through the O7A Upmixers VST plug-in suite mentioned

⁹ The description on the Blue Ripple website states: "This mode is optimised for use with material that has been mixed using conventional panning techniques, such as equal-power panning or VBAP. The approach produces smooth transitions when sounds pass between speaker locations." - <https://www.blueripplesound.com/index>

¹⁰ A Reaper template with filters for standard mic arrays is available here: <https://www.brucewiggins.co.uk/?p=2041>

Figure 1. Binaural conversion process of channel-based and Ambisonics composition through Upmixing and Decoding for the final formats *Stereo*, *Binaural* and *Binaural+*

above, but there are alternatives to this process, including the use of Bruce Wiggins' UHQ Decoder/Transcoder, which encodes stereo differently¹¹.

One could argue that it makes more sense to take the direct route when converting channel-based formats such as 5.1 to stereo via a downmix matrix. But in several listening sessions with Waves DTS Neural Downmix and Nx VST plug-ins working with a mixing matrix, the method of transcoding to Ambisonics sounded preferable. Another reason for decoding channel-based formats into Ambisonics is to facilitate future implementation of dynamic conversion, head tracking, and streaming, which will be easier to achieve if the compositions are encoded in Ambisonics.

A visualization of the workflow can be seen in Figure 1. A Reaper template was created to handle the entire conversion process. WAV was chosen as the high quality backup format, while WebM was used for the online presentation.

4. CONCLUSION

The presented binaural conversion workflow for multi-channel electroacoustic compositions addresses key challenges in adapting spatial audio for headphone listening. The technical and artistic choices balance practical feasibility with preservation of compositional intent, particularly through careful use of room virtualization and spatial processing. The approach presented seeks to enhance binaural reproduction while contributing to the ongoing discussion of standards and practices in the field.

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¹¹ <https://www.brucewiggins.co.uk/?p=1836>

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